

Preparation and Properties of N-Hydroxy-N,N'-diarylbenzamidines

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The synthesis and characteristics of N-hydroxy-N-p-chlorophenyl-N'-phenylbenzamidine and ten analogous hydroxyamidines are described. On the basis of infrared studies of these compounds, the important group frequencies have been assigned.

THE chemistry of hydroxyamidines is of recent interest. They have been found to be valuable organic analytical reagents for the gravimetric and spectrophotometric analysis of metal ions.^{1,2} This group of compounds contain bidentate functional grouping (I) and are prepared by the condensation of N-arylbenzimidoyl chlorides and N-aryl-hydroxylamines in absolute ether medium.

N-Arylbenzimidoyl chlorides can be obtained by several methods.^{3,4} In the present investigation all the N-arylbenzimidoyl chlorides were prepared following essentially the method of Wallach^{5,6} by the action of thionyl chloride on corresponding anilides. The condensation of N-arylbenzimidoyl chloride (II) and N-arylhydroxylamine leads to N-hydroxy-N,N'-diarylbenzamidine hydrochloride (III) which on treatment with dilute ammonia liberates hydroxyamidine free base (IV).

Eleven hydroxyamidines reported in this communication for the first time, were synthesised with the object of using them as possible organo-analytical reagents. Infrared spectra, analyses, m.p. and storage qualities for the characterisation of these compounds are described.

Experimental

Materials and apparatus: All the chemicals used were BDH/KochLight/Fluka products. Melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Infrared spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer Spectrophotometer—221 equipped with sodium chloride optics.

General method of preparation: To a solution of 9.9 g of N-phenylbenzimidoyl chloride (0.044 mole) in 100 ml of cold absolute ether taken in a 500 ml conical flask provided with a bent glass rod, an ice cold solution of 6.5 g of N-p-chlorophenylhydroxylamine (0.045 mole) in 50ml absolute ether was added over a period of 10 min in small quantities with constant shaking. A light-brown oil separated which on shaking for 30 min solidified into white shining crystals resembling sodium chloride. The crude N-hydroxy-N-p-chlorophenyl-N'-phenylbenzamidine hydrochloride thus obtained was filtered, washed with 3 × 20 ml portions of absolute ether and air dried. Yield, 12. lg.

Isolation of free base: The crude hydrochloride was treated with 30 ml of 5N ammonia and the precipitated pale yellow crystals of the free base were filtered and washed with distilled water. The free base was crystallised from petroleum ether (60-80°): benzene (1 : 2) to get silky crystals. Yield, 8.0g (50%).

The properties of five free bases and six hydrochlorides are summarised in Table 1. Hydrochlorides, 6-11 (Table 1) on treatment with ammonia, however, resulted into oily products. These hydrochlorides were crystallised from minimum volume of absolute alcohol to which few drops of concentrated hydrochloric acid were added. Attempts to crystallise the hydrochlorides of the free bases, 1-5 (Table 1) always lead to free bases.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF HYDROXYAMIDINES

Compound No	—benzamide	Mol. formula	M.P. °C	Yield %	Analysis %					
					Found			Calc.		
					C	H	N	C	H	N
1.	N-Hydroxy-N- <i>p</i> -chlorophenyl-N'-phenyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ N ₂ OCl	150	50	70.95	4.92	8.45	70.72	4.65	8.67
2.	N-Hydroxy-N- <i>p</i> -chlorophenyl-N'- <i>m</i> -tolyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ N ₂ OCl	155	40	71.95	5.20	8.39	71.64	5.05	8.32
3.	N-Hydroxy-N- <i>p</i> -chlorophenyl-N'- <i>p</i> -tolyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ N ₂ OCl	160-61	45	72.00	5.25	8.49	71.64	5.05	8.32
4.	N-Hydroxy-N,N'-di- <i>p</i> -chlorophenyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ N ₂ OCl ₂	142	42	64.15	4.11	7.62	63.90	3.92	7.84
5.	N-Hydroxy-N- <i>p</i> -chlorophenyl-N'- <i>p</i> -anisyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	151	70	68.50	5.02	7.84	68.11	4.85	7.91
6.	N-Hydroxy-N- <i>p</i> -chlorophenyl-N'-(2:4 dimethyl phenyl)-hydrochloride	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₂ OCl ₂	189	70	65.70	5.12	7.07	65.15	5.17	7.23
7.	N-Hydroxy-N- <i>p</i> -chlorophenyl-N'-(2:5 dimethyl phenyl)-hydrochloride	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₂ OCl ₂	195-96	65	65.06	5.02	7.41	65.15	5.17	7.23
8.	N-Hydroxy-N- <i>p</i> -chlorophenyl-N'-(2:6 dimethyl phenyl)-hydrochloride	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₂ OCl ₂	185	75	65.60	5.66	7.11	65.15	5.17	7.23
9.	N-Hydroxy-N- <i>p</i> -chlorophenyl-N'- <i>o</i> -tolyl, -hydrochloride	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ OCl ₂	178	45	64.20	4.71	7.65	64.38	4.82	7.50
10.	N-Hydroxy-N- <i>p</i> -chlorophenyl-N'- <i>o</i> -chlorophenyl, -hydrochloride	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₂ OCl ₂	159	40	57.50	3.98	7.35	57.97	3.81	7.10
11.	N-Hydroxy-N- <i>p</i> -chlorophenyl-N'-benzyl, -hydrochloride	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ OCl ₂	163	70	64.70	4.92	7.59	64.38	4.82	7.52

Results and Discussion

All the reactions resulted into 40-75% yields. The time required for complete solidification of the light-brown oil varied between 10-90 min. The free bases are pale yellow substances while the hydrochlorides are white crystalline solids.

It is interesting to note that the treatment of the hydrochloride in which a benzyl or an orthosubstituted phenyl group is incorporated at the azomethine nitrogen, with ammonia always resulted into oily products.

The compounds were crystallised at least three times and vacuum dried. These reagents are sparingly soluble in water, carbon tetrachloride, chlorobenzene, moderately soluble in acetone, benzene, ethyl acetate and freely so in chloroform and ethanol. They are stable to heat, light and air and can be stored for a long time without deterioration. The solutions of the reagents in various organic solvents are stable for several days when stored in amber coloured bottles. This storage property is of great use from analytical stand point.

The important group frequencies in infrared region are shown in Table 2.

The OH stretching absorption in hydroxyamidines appears at 3085 cm⁻¹ indicative of strong intramolecular hydrogen bonding.⁷ The C=N bond stretching bands have been assigned in the 1595-1600 cm⁻¹ region on the basis of available data in amidines.^{8,9} It may be noted that intramolecular hydrogen bonding has no influence on the C=N stretching absorption. The C=N absorption in amidines occurs around 1600 cm⁻¹. In hydroxyamidines also the absorption occurs at the same region despite the presence of strong intramolecular hydrogen bonding. The hydroxyamidines hydrochlorides have also been examined and the characteristic C=NH¹⁰ and =NH^{11,12} absorptions have been assigned in the regions 1610-1625 and 2525-2750 cm⁻¹ respectively. A sharp band at 3030-3055 cm⁻¹ has been assigned to aromatic C-H stretch. The frequency of this band does not correlate too much with the molecular environment.

TABLE 2—INFRARED GROUP FREQUENCIES IN HYDROXYAMIDINES (IN CM⁻¹)

Compound No (Table 1)	OH	=C-H (Aromatic)	=NH ⁺ (Ammonium band)	C=NH ⁺ (Ammonium band)	C=N	C-N	N-O
1	3085	3030	—	—	1600 S	1430 S	940
2	3085	3050	—	—	1600 S	1420 S	920
3	3085	3050	—	—	1600 S	1440 S	940
4	3085	3055	—	—	1595 S	1440 S	940
5	3085	3055	—	—	1600 S	1440 S	940
6	—	3045	2750 B	1620 S	—	1440 S	945
7	—	3050	2540 B	1615 S	—	1440 S	935
8	—	3050	2525 B	1610 S	—	1440 S	940
9	—	3050	2550 B	1615 S	—	1440 S	950
10	—	3050	2560 B	1620 S	—	1440 S	940
11	—	3050	2580 B	1625 S	—	1440 S	945

Spectra 1-8 recorded in nujol. Spectra 9-11 recorded in hexachlorobutadiene (3700-1800 cm⁻¹ and 1500-1300 cm⁻¹) and nujol (1800-1500 cm⁻¹ and 1300-650 cm⁻¹)
B—broad; S—sharp.

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